

ISic3639

I.Sicily inscription 3639

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Melita

Place of origin (modern)

Malta

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Valletta, Malta, National Archaeological Museum

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR113464

1. ((luna crescente))
2. D (iis) M (anibus) .
3. Elvius Titus
4. vixit annos
5. LV, cives be
6. ne merenti
7. fecerunt.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285185

EDR 113464

EDCS 23400467

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.8319 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3639. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388880>